
Crania antiqua (Defrance, 1818) from the Late Maastrichtian
'Tuffeau jaunâtre à Thecidea papillata'-bed (Jauche Member)

Nick VAN LIEFFERINGE

TAXONOMY

Kingdom: Animalia

Phylum: Brachiopoda

Class: Craniata

Order: Craniida

Family: Craniidae

Genus: *Crania*

Species: *Crania antiqua*

Author Citation: Defrance, 1818

GEOLOGICAL TIME SCALE

Eon: Phanerozoic

Era: Mesozoic

Period: Cretaceous

Sub Period: None

Epoch: Late

International Age: Maastrichtian

STRATIGRAPHY

The fossils are associated with a coarse-grained biocalcarenite ("Tuffeau jaunâtre à Thecidea papillata"-bed), part of the (Late Maastrichtian) Jauche Member (**Bless et al.** 1990).

PROVENANCE

Collector: Nick Van Liefferinge (NVL)

Date Collected: 21/02/2026

Acquired by: Field collection

LOCATION

Jauche-la-Marne

Orp-Jauche

Walloon Brabant

Belgium

REFERENCES

Bless M.J.M., Felder P.J. & Jagt J.W.M. 1990: Repeated Tethyan influences in the Early Campanian to Middle Late Maastrichtian successions of Folx-les-Caves and Orp-le-Petit (Eastern Brabant Massif, Belgium), *Annales de la Société Géologique de Belgique*, T. 113 (fascicule 2), pp. 179-197.

Simon E. 1981: Maastrichtian brachiopods from Ciply: palaeoecological and stratigraphical significance. *Bulletin de l'Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Sciences de la Terre* 68, pp. 181-232.

<Fig. 1>

Crania antiqua (Defrance, 1818). Adult ventral valve: (a) exterior view, (b) interior view.